

HYDROPHILIZATION OF PET USING DBD PLASMA

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ABSTRACT

Polyester is a most common material used in modern engineering. 0.4% moisture regain makes it highly hydrophobic, which is favorable for water harvesting. Our work utilizes a parallel-plate non-thermal plasma dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) system worked at medium pressure in dry air and nitrogen gas to change the surface characterization of non-woven polyethylene terephthalate (PET) fabric. The surface modification of PET fabric was determined by water contact angle (WCA), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and wettability analysis. WCA, XPS and wettability results showed that DBD plasma treatment on PET fabric improved the hydrophilicity. A reduction in contact angle more within 5 minutes for air and nitrogen discharges was noticed as compared to untreated sample. XPS measurements revealed an increase in the presence of polar functional groups, indicating that the induced surface changes are mostly chemical in nature. The XPS analysis is good agreement with WCA. In terms of oxygen plasma treatment, changes were seen in XPS spectra of the peak C 1s, whereas the changes with nitrogen-plasma treatment were less pronounced. Water adsorption time was observed much fast for air and nitrogen treatment respectively as compared to untreated fabric when the fabrics were immersed into water immediately after plasma exposure.

1 INTRODUCTION

The textile industry is facing many issues, the surface modification of synthetic fibers being one of them. Poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET), commonly referred to as polyester, is considered to be one of the most important polymers in the industry thanks to its many interesting properties, including its high strength, formability, dimensional and thermal stability, degree of hardness and excellent chemical properties [1, 2]. The main downside of PET is its very hydrophobic nature with only 0.42% moisture regains, which makes it very challenging for aqueous post production processes such as dyeing and makes it not suitable for possible water harvesting applications, as textile should absorb and transport liquid for water harvesting applications. To overcome this disadvantage, chemical modifications [3] have been studied to make the PET fabrics more hydrophilic. These modifications, generally referred to as moisture management, depend upon the type and structure of fibre or fabric, the finishing applied to the material and other possible post production processes. As the structural integrity of PET meshes often becomes compromised after chemical modifications, numerous alternative methods have been reported to improve their degree of hydrophilization.

Non-thermal plasma treatment is one of the most promising modification technologies that has been reported in the field of surface modification over last decade [4, 5]. Plasma technology gained interest because of its capacity to effectively change the wettability, and this without the use of solvents and a low consumption of power. In parallel, these modifications also tend to change the textile adhesion properties [6]. Especially atmospheric pressure plasma systems are considered to be of interest, as the lack of expensive vacuum equipment allows for their straightforward in-line implementation in industrial processes.

It is well known that plasma treatments, when operated under the optimal conditions, using inert gases such as air or nitrogen, only affect the first few subsurface atomic layers, while preserving the overall

bulk properties [4] [7]. A number of research articles have been reported on the plasma reactors at atmospheric pressure [8-11]. By utilizing in textile industry, this technology can be integrated in a constant production or finishing department. Hence, vacuum technology is recognized as being non-competitive. Although, Poll et al [4] narrated that long time treatment is significantly affective for the penetration into textile structures. Similarly, Vatuna et al [12] also observed the penetration after a 20 min treatment time of different textile layers with an atmospheric plasma. However, Poll et al [4] proposed a pressure range from 0.1 to 10 kPa for optimal plasma modification of voluminous textile structure for all type of thickness. Therefore, medium pressure is relatively economical and favorable over atmospheric pressure for the textile structure.

Dielectric barrier discharges are being experimented at industrial scale, e.g. ozone production, surface modification [13-15] and gas cleaning. In this study, non woven polyester sheets were treated with parallel-plate medium pressure DBD plasma (5.0 kPa) in dry air and nitrogen. XPS, WCA, water absorption time, and vertical wicking test were employed to characterize the untreated and plasma treated non-woven PET.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Non woven polyethylene terephthalate fabric sheet was used in the size of $10 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$ for DBD plasma treatment. All the samples were exposed to ultrasonic (VWR, 90% pure) to remove any superficial impurity. A parallel-plate DBD system operated at medium pressure [1] was utilized to treat the polyester. The DBD system was consist of two copper electrodes (Ø : 50mm) covered with glass plates. The gap between two plates was 35 mm. The upper electrode was attached to 50 KHz AC voltages and lower electrode was attached to 50Ω .

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of DBD reactor

The system was filled with air or nitrogen at 3 standard liters per minute (slm) up to 50 kPa and the plasma reactor was flushed at 3 slm for 3 min to achieve a reproducible discharge as shown in figure 1. Samples were treated with dry air and N_2 gas and then characterized for WCA, XPS and wettability tests.

Goniometry

Plasma treated samples were subjected to static water contact angle measurements within 5 min after treatment, using a Krüss Easy Drop optical system (Krüss GmbH, Hamburg, and Germany). A 1 microliter drop volume was used and the contact angles were automatically measured within 3 second using the Laplace–Young curve fitting procedure. All the contact angle measurements described in this paper is the mean of 5 random measurements over each sample with standard deviations consistently diversifying between 0.1° and 2.5° .

XPS analysis

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy was performed on a PHI 5000 Versaprobe II system (ULVAC-Physical Electronics, Chigasaki, Japan) equipped with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source (h ν = 1486.6 eV) operated at 23.3 W.

Water Absorption Time

The absorption rate of the samples with respect to time was measured accordance to standard method AATCC 79. A droplet of 5 μ l was poured from 1 cm above the substrate onto the surface of the tested substrate. The total time for the disappearance of the reflection from the liquid surface was considered to be the wettability of the specimen. The shorter absorption time results in better wettability.

Vertical wicking

An in-house method was used that was adapted to the Czech standard (Czech national ČSN 80 08 28), which quantifies the suction of a water droplet into the sample. 250 x 10 mm² samples were immobilized within the instrument. An ink drop was put into the reservoir to visualize the height of water on the sample suspended vertically to calculate the results [16].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

WCA

The treatment of DBD plasma measurements are directly related to the water WCA of the substrate used for this study. After being plasma treated with dry air and nitrogen gas, the WCA of the polyester are presented in the figure 2. The contact angle of the plasma treated samples showed a remarkable difference compared to the untreated sample. The contact angle is relatively inversely proportional to the time. With the increase in time period the contact angle decreased to a certain limit for both treated samples. Afterward, contact angle did not change particularly.

Fig. 2. Water contact angle measurements for plasma activated non woven polyester fabric for dry air and N₂

XPS analysis

The XPS analysis indicates that the formation of C-O and C=O O-C=O groups on the surface of polyester. To know about the nature of functional groups which were formed by plasma treatment, the atomic composition of both untreated, and plasma treated samples was measured by XPS [2].

Table 1. N/C, O/C and ratio

Sample	C1s (At.%)	N1s (At.%)	O1s (At.%)	N/C ratio (%)	O/C (%)
Untreated	75.4	1	23.4	1.3	31
Dry Air	66.6	1.9	31.5	2.8	47
Nitrogen	67.8	5.6	26.5	8.3	39.1

The O/C and N/C atomic ratios for the untreated sample and plasma treated samples are given in Table 1. O/C ratio of samples plasma treated with dry air treated are predicted higher (47%) than untreated (31%) and nitrogen treated (39%) sample. O/C ratio, N/C ratio and (N+O)/C ratio as a function of energy density for the polyester samples are given in Table 1. O/C ratio of dry air samples is predicted to be higher (47%) than that of untreated (31%) and nitrogen (39%) samples. The higher value reveals that new oxygen-containing groups appeared on the substrate after plasma treatment with dry air, but they appeared in lower concentrations in cases of nitrogen plasma treatment.

Fig. 3. C1s curve fit for dry air plasma activated non woven polyester fabric

The higher ratio of O/C also resulted in a lower water contact angle and higher wettability. The formation of oxygen-containing functional groups increased the hydrophilicity of the polymer used for this study.

For the plasma treated samples, it can be observed that air plasma treatment increases the C-O peak and incorporates the oxygen functionalities. Moreover, nitrogen plasma treatment also effectively disintegrates the C-O bonds and the comprising oxygen functional groups as shown in figure 3 (b,c). In contrast, the concentration of C=O decreased with the increase in binding energy. For the C-O and O-C=O component, a significant increase in the peaks was observed that is favorable for the water adhesion to the surface of the PET substrate. XPS interpretation of PET samples introduced a new C-COO component on the surface after plasma treatment that is also desired for the minimal contact angle. Plasma treatment with dry air produced oxygen-containing functional groups on the surface of polyester samples. The deconvoluted C1s peaks of untreated and plasma-treated samples are depicted in Figure 3. The C1s peak of untreated specimen carries four different peaks at 284.8, 286.1, 286.9 and 288.9 eV corresponding to $\underline{\text{C}}\text{-C}$, $\underline{\text{C}}\text{-O}$ and $\underline{\text{C}}\text{-N}$, $\underline{\text{C}}=\text{O}$ and $\text{O}-\underline{\text{C}}=\text{O}$ respectively. After treatment with air plasma, an additional peak is introduced at 287.8 eV corresponding to $\underline{\text{C}}=\text{O}$ bonds. After nitrogen treatment, that peak is characterized with an additional shoulder just above 288.0 eV which could be linked to amide bonds. Therefore, an additional peak at 285.7 eV, as shown in figure 3, was found corresponding to $\underline{\text{C}}\text{-COO}$.

Water absorption time

Fig. 4. Water absorption time

The water absorption time explains the first contact of water with the substrate. As the water droplets poured onto the surface of untreated and plasma treated samples, no immediate absorption was noticed for all of them. But, after 22 and 27 minutes the reflection of droplets disappeared and 100% wettability of air and nitrogen plasma treated samples was observed respectively. On the other hand, the droplets on the surface of untreated fabric showed the 100% wettability after 112 minutes as presented in figure 4.

Vertical wicking height

Vertical wicking height is the distance water wicks up in fabric driven by capillarity against the gravity. The behavior of capillary force in untreated and plasma-treated samples was slightly changed. Untreated samples reflected the vertical wicking height from 0–1mm for 1–30 min, respectively and plasma-treated (air and nitrogen) showed vertical wicking height from 0–2 mm for 1–30 min, respectively, as shown in figure 5. The low value of vertical wicking indicates the material is porous and has no capillary mechanism to propagate the water.

Fig. 5. Vertical wicking height

Conclusion

Wetting and hydrophilic characteristics of non-woven polyester fibre PET increased after air and nitrogen plasma treatment, caused by the formation of C=O and O–C=O polar groups on the surface of the substrate while inadequate nitrogen-containing groups were observed, as presented in XPS analysis. WCA of the plasma-treated samples displayed a high significant difference compared to that of the untreated polyester sample. WCA of the samples decreased to a minimum level and slightly increased after 5 minutes treatment so this time duration consider optimal for rest of measurements. The XPS analysis clearly verified the incorporation of functional groups on the surface after both DBD oxygen and nitrogen plasma treatment. In terms of oxygen plasma treatment, significant changes were seen in XPS spectra of the peak C 1s with energy density, whereas the changes with nitrogen-plasma treatment were less pronounced. Water absorption time vertical wicking reinforced the results and indicated the presence of various functional groups on the surface of non-woven polyester leads to better surface modification characteristic which would make the plasma-activated PET non-woven ideal substrates for water harvesting.

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